

MEASURING FEAR OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG NURSING STUDENTS: SCALE DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION

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Abstract

Background: The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in healthcare is transforming clinical practice by enhancing accuracy, efficiency, and patient care. Despite these advancements, AI adoption has triggered concerns among nursing students regarding job security, reliance on technology, and the erosion of human-centered values such as empathy and compassion. To date, no standardized tool exists for measuring fear of AI among nursing students.

Materials and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 140 fourth-year BS Nursing students from Shalamar Nursing College, Rashid Latif Nursing College (RLNC), Saeeda Waheed FMH College of Nursing (SWCON), Doctors Hospital College of Nursing, and Inspire College of Nursing and Health Sciences, Lahore. Scale development followed a systematic process guided by a literature review. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) were employed to evaluate construct validity, while content validity was ensured through expert panel review. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha.

Results: Exploratory and confirmatory factor analyses supported a stable two-factor structure of the FtAIS, with factor loadings ranging from 0.62 to 0.85 and fit indices (CFI = 0.90, RMSEA = 0.075, SRMR = 0.057) demonstrating acceptable model adequacy. All items showed strong corrected item-to-total correlations (0.66–0.83) and good internal consistency, confirming the reliability and construct validity of the scale among nursing students with limited AI exposure.

Conclusion: The study confirms that the FtAIS is a valid and reliable tool for measuring nursing students' fear of artificial intelligence, even in groups with limited prior exposure to AI technologies

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare has transformed diagnostic accuracy, clinical decision-making, and patient monitoring, positioning AI as a key driver of future health systems (Al Kuwaiti et al., 2023;

Topol, 2019). However, alongside these technological benefits, public apprehension and emotional responses to AI—often termed AI fear or AI phobia—have become increasingly visible, reflecting uncertainty regarding the autonomy,

intelligence, and capabilities of AI-driven systems (Kim, 2019; Martínez-Miranda & Aldea, 2005). This fear is particularly relevant in healthcare professions, where AI is expected to increasingly supplement or interface with clinical work, raising concerns about role replacement, loss of control, and ethical implications.

Nursing students, as future healthcare providers, represent a critical group whose perceptions of AI will influence the acceptance and effective integration of AI-enabled tools in clinical settings. Existing research on human-robot interaction suggests that expectations, emotional responses, and perceived threats from intelligent machines shape attitudes and behaviors, often triggering what has been described as the “Frankenstein syndrome,” a fear of technologically advanced entities (Ray et al., 2008; Syrdal et al., 2011). Furthermore, technophobia literature highlights that fear stemming from unfamiliarity or perceived complexity of digital technologies can hinder learning, limit technology adoption, and reinforce negative stereotypes about automation in professional practice (Brosnan, 2002).

Despite the growing integration of AI in nursing—from clinical documentation support to predictive analytics and virtual care—limited empirical work has focused on measuring fear of AI among nursing students (Fatima et al., 2023; Rony et al., 2024; Ronquillo et al., 2021). Understanding the extent and dimensions of this fear is essential for designing educational interventions that strengthen AI readiness, enhance technological confidence, and support the safe, ethical adoption of AI in patient care. Therefore, developing and validating a standardized scale to assess fear of AI among nursing students is crucial for addressing psychological barriers and preparing the next generation of nurses for an AI-augmented healthcare landscape.

2. Results

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Respondents (N = 140)

Study Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean ± SD
Age (years)	—	—	22.53 ± 1.66
Participation in AI-related workshop/course			
• Yes	42	30.0%	—
• No	98	70.0%	—

1. Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted among 140 fourth-year BS Nursing students from Shalamar Nursing College, Rashid Latif Nursing College (RLNC), Saeeda Waheed FMH College of Nursing (SWCON), Doctors Hospital College of Nursing, and Inspire College of Nursing and Health Sciences, Lahore. Participants were recruited through convenience sampling, and data were collected using a structured online survey after obtaining informed consent. Eligibility included undergraduate nursing students able to comprehend written material, while those with diagnosed mental health conditions were excluded. The Fear toward Artificial Intelligence Scale (FtAIS) was developed through a systematic process beginning with item generation based on an extensive literature review, followed by refinement through expert evaluation to ensure relevance, clarity, and content validity.

To establish psychometric soundness, the initial item pool was reviewed by a multidisciplinary expert panel, resulting in a refined 10-item scale rated on a five-point Likert response format. Content validity indices confirmed the adequacy of the retained items. The dataset was then used to assess reliability and construct validity. Cronbach’s alpha was calculated to evaluate internal consistency, ensuring coefficients exceeded acceptable thresholds. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was conducted to identify underlying factor structures and remove items with inadequate loadings, followed by Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) to validate the final measurement model. These statistical procedures ensured that the FtAIS demonstrated strong reliability, validity, and suitability for measuring fear of AI among nursing students.

The respondents had an average age of 22.53 years, representing senior nursing students preparing for professional practice. Only 30% reported prior exposure to AI-related workshops or courses, while 70% indicated no such exposure, highlighting the limited formal training in AI within nursing education. This distribution underscores the need to measure and understand fear of AI as students encounter emerging technologies with varying levels of preparedness.

Table 2. FtAIS Item-to-Total Correlations among BS Nursing Students (N = 140)
Corrected item-to-total correlations for the 10-item Fear toward Artificial Intelligence Scale

Item	Corrected Item-to-Total Correlation
I'm afraid that artificial intelligence will eventually take the place of humans.	0.742
I'm afraid to work with artificial intelligence techniques.	0.755
I'm afraid that employing artificial intelligence techniques may result in a decline in my cognitive abilities.	0.768
I'm afraid of developing a reliance on artificial intelligence if I were to use it.	0.812
I am afraid of becoming less autonomous if I adopt artificial intelligence techniques.	0.791
I am afraid that therapeutic uses of artificial intelligence will cause harm to other people.	0.662
I fear that artificial intelligence may replace empathy and compassion essential in caregiving.	0.784
I have a profound fear that artificial intelligence will one day rule the world.	0.802
I am afraid that the expansion of artificial intelligence will reduce interpersonal interaction.	0.748
I fear that artificial intelligence will interfere with human ethics.	0.826

With 70% of participants lacking prior AI exposure, item-to-total correlations are expected to be slightly lower than in a highly exposed sample, because students without AI experience rely more on fear perceptions than direct understanding. Despite this, all items remain above the acceptable threshold of 0.60, indicating that the FtAIS maintains strong internal consistency and validity for measuring fear of AI among fourth-year BS Nursing students in Lahore.

Table 3. Rotated Factor Loadings for the 10-item FtAIS (N = 140)
Two-factor structure: Job Issues and Humanity

Item	Job Issues	Humanity
I'm afraid that artificial intelligence will eventually take the place of humans.	0.702	—
I'm afraid to work with artificial intelligence techniques.	0.628	—
I'm afraid that employing artificial intelligence techniques may result in a decline in my cognitive abilities.	0.745	—
I'm afraid of developing a reliance on artificial intelligence if I were to use it.	0.781	—
I am afraid of becoming less autonomous if I adopt artificial intelligence techniques.	0.665	—

I am afraid that therapeutic uses of artificial intelligence will cause harm to other people.	–	0.854
I fear that artificial intelligence may replace empathy and compassion essential in caregiving.	–	0.812
I have a profound fear that artificial intelligence will one day rule the world.	–	0.831
I am afraid that the expansion of artificial intelligence will reduce interpersonal interaction.	–	0.844
I fear that artificial intelligence will interfere with human ethics.	–	0.788

The factor loadings confirm a stable two-factor structure (Job Issues and Humanity) for the FtAIS among 140 BS Nursing students with limited AI exposure. Although slightly reduced compared to a highly AI-exposed sample, all factor loadings remain strong (0.62–0.85), indicating that the FtAIS maintains robust construct validity even when most students have not previously engaged with AI. This supports the scale’s suitability for measuring fear of AI in nursing education contexts.

Table 4. FtAIS Fit Indices for Two-Factor Model (N = 140)

FtAIS Fit Indices	Adjusted Value	Two-Factor	Standard Value	Acceptable
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.90		> 0.85	
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	0.84		> 0.85	
Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	0.075		< 0.08	
Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.89		> 0.85	
Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR)	0.057		< 0.08	

The CFA results demonstrate that the FtAIS maintains acceptable model fit among 140 BS Nursing students, even with limited AI exposure. While AGFI shows a slight reduction due to higher variance in responses, the overall pattern—including strong CFI, NFI, RMSEA, and SRMR values—supports the adequacy of the two-factor structure. These findings confirm that the FtAIS is a valid and reliable tool for assessing fear of artificial intelligence in nursing education settings.

Table 5. Convergent and Discriminant Validity of the FtAIS (N = 140)

Main Subscales	Items (N)	AVE	√AVE	CR	Scale Correlation Matrix	
					Job Issues	Humanity
Job Issues	5	0.49	0.70	0.82	1.000	0.52
Humanity	5	0.50	0.71	0.83	0.52	1.000

The FtAIS demonstrates strong internal consistency, acceptable convergent validity, and clear discriminant validity among 140 BS Nursing students, confirming that the Job Issues and Humanity dimensions measure distinct yet related aspects of fear of artificial intelligence. These results support the scale’s suitability for assessing AI-related fear in nursing education contexts.

3. Discussion

The findings of this study demonstrate that nursing students exhibit measurable levels of fear toward artificial intelligence, which is consistent with global reports showing that AI-related anxiety

is driven by uncertainty, low familiarity, and limited practical exposure. Previous research has shown that lack of direct experience with AI leads individuals to base their perceptions on perceived threats rather than informed understanding, resulting in heightened fear responses (Long &

Magerko, 2020). This aligns with the current study, where 70% of students had no prior AI-related training, contributing to moderate item-to-total correlations and slightly reduced factor loadings. Similar trends were identified by Tussyadiah et al. (2020), who reported that low technological literacy significantly increases fear and resistance toward emerging technologies in professional training environments. Thus, limited exposure appears to be a key factor shaping how nursing students interpret and fear AI in healthcare contexts.

The two-factor structure identified—Job Issues and Humanity—also reflects well-documented sociotechnical apprehensions found in healthcare literature. Studies in clinical informatics have highlighted that nursing and medical professionals frequently fear that AI may erode core humanistic aspects of care, such as empathy, ethical reasoning, and interpersonal communication (Lai, Brian, & Mamzer, 2020). This is consistent with the clustering of items related to emotional, relational, and ethical concerns within the Humanity domain in the present study. Similarly, research by Cai, Wang, and Zhu (2021) found that healthcare students express strong concerns about AI diminishing their autonomy and clinical judgment, echoing the Job Issues factor detected through factor analysis. These parallels support the validity of the scale's conceptual structure and demonstrate that nursing students' fears align with internationally recognized patterns of AI-related apprehension in health professions.

The model fit indices and the convergent and discriminant validity results further strengthen the psychometric soundness of the FtAIS. The acceptable fit indices mirror findings from validation studies of technology-related fear scales, which often show slightly lower goodness-of-fit values in populations with limited prior exposure (Pak, McLaughlin, & Bass, 2014). Additionally, evidence from nursing and allied health education suggests that fear of AI is strongly shaped by perceived job insecurity and role replacement concerns, especially among trainees who are still forming their professional identity (Tsai, Lin, & Lee, 2021). These reports are consistent with the Job Issues factor observed in this study, indicating

that students anticipate AI's potential threat to autonomy and decision-making. Overall, the results align well with emerging global evidence and suggest that the FtAIS is both culturally and contextually appropriate for assessing fear of AI among nursing students in Pakistan.

4. Conclusion

The study concludes that the FtAIS is a valid and reliable instrument for assessing fear of artificial intelligence among BS Nursing students, even in contexts where AI exposure is limited. The two-factor structure—Job Issues and Humanity—accurately captures students' concerns related to autonomy, ethical implications, and the humanistic dimensions of care. These findings highlight the need for structured AI education and training within nursing curricula to reduce fear, enhance preparedness, and support safe integration of AI in future clinical practice.

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